

Identifies Several Common and Significant Aquatic Plants In Several Rural Area of Bangladesh

Md.Nahid Mahmud

College of Agricultural Sciences, IUBAT

Abstract

Aquatic plants, encompassing a diverse array of species, play a crucial role in freshwater and marine ecosystems. These organisms, which include submerged, floating, and emergent varieties, contribute significantly to biodiversity, water quality, and habitat structure. They facilitate nutrient cycling, provide oxygen through photosynthesis, and serve as vital food sources for aquatic organisms. Furthermore, aquatic plants offer essential ecosystem services, such as erosion control and water filtration. The health of aquatic plant communities is often an indicator of environmental quality, making them important for monitoring ecosystem health and resilience. Understanding the dynamics of these plants is vital for effective conservation and management strategies, especially in the face of climate change and human impact.

Keywords

Aquatic plants, Identifies, Description, Habitat, Taxonomy

Introduction

Aquatic plants, often referred to as macrophytes, are a diverse group of vegetation that thrive in water environments, including freshwater lakes, rivers, wetlands, and marine ecosystems. They play a pivotal role in maintaining the health and functionality of aquatic habitats. These plants are typically categorized into several groups based on their growth forms and ecological niches: submerged, floating, and emergent plants.

Submerged plants, such as eelgrass and hornwort, grow entirely underwater and are crucial for oxygen production and providing habitat for fish and invertebrates. Floating plants, like water lilies and duckweed, float on the water's surface, offering shade and reducing evaporation, while also serving as food for various wildlife. Emergent plants, such as cattails and bulrushes, grow partially above the water level, creating essential transitions between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems.

Aquatic plants have adapted to various environmental conditions, developing unique features such as specialized root systems, buoyant leaves, and intricate reproductive strategies. These adaptations allow them to thrive in diverse settings, from shallow ponds to deeper lakes and coastal waters. Their growth not only supports aquatic life but also contributes to sediment stabilization, preventing erosion along shorelines and riverbanks.

The ecological importance of aquatic plants extends to their role in nutrient cycling. They absorb excess nutrients and pollutants from the water, improving overall water quality. This filtering capability is vital for preventing algal blooms and maintaining a balanced ecosystem. Moreover, through photosynthesis, aquatic plants generate significant amounts of oxygen, which is essential for the survival of aquatic organisms.

Beyond their ecological contributions, aquatic plants hold economic and recreational value. They are integral to fisheries, providing habitat for commercially important fish species. Additionally, many people enjoy recreational activities such as boating, fishing, and birdwatching in areas rich with aquatic vegetation. These plants also enhance the aesthetic appeal of natural landscapes, making them popular in landscaping and garden design.

In recent years, the conservation of aquatic plants has become increasingly important due to threats from pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change. Protecting these vital plants is crucial for sustaining healthy aquatic ecosystems and ensuring the well-being of the myriad species that depend on them, including humans. Understanding and appreciating the multifaceted roles of aquatic plants can help foster efforts to preserve these invaluable resources for future generations.

Serial Number	Local Name	English Name	Scientific Name
01	Kutkute jhanjhi	Hydrilla	<i>Hydrila verticillate(L.)</i>
02	Kochuripana	Water Hyacinths	<i>Pontederia crassipes(L.)</i>
03	Helencha	Buffalo spinach	<i>Enhydra fluctuans(L.)</i>
04	Kolmi	Water spinach	<i>Ipomea Acquatica(L.)</i>
05	Khtipana	Water lenses or Duckweeds	<i>Azolla pinnata(L.)</i>
06	Guripana or Sujipana	Rootless duckweed	<i>Wolffia arrhizal(L.)</i>
07	Tetuliapana	Common duckweed	<i>Lemna minor.</i>
08	Shapla	Water lilies	<i>Nymphaea nouchali L.</i>
09	Padma	Lotus	<i>Nelumbo nucifera L.</i>
10	Nolkhagra Panighash	Common spikerush	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>
11	Panifol	Water chestnuts	<i>Trapa natans</i>
12	Hiozol	Indian oak	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>
13	Pani kochu	Taro	<i>Colocasia esculentta</i>
14	Joloj agacha	Grassy pondweed	<i>Potamogeton gramineus</i>
15	Kokra pata	Curly pondweed	<i>Potamogeton crispus L.</i>

16	Chandramala	Banana lily	<i>Nymphodies aquatica</i>
17	Boronakha	heartleaf false pickerelweed	<i>Monochoria hastata</i>
18	Nazas	Brittle waternymph	<i>Najas minor</i>
19	Gomoti	Yellow lotus	<i>Nelumbo lutea</i>
20	Holud amrul or Amrul shak	Creeping woodsorrel	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>

Hydrilla

Hydrilla grows Along the bottoms of Wetlands, Rivers, Streams, Lakes, And Ponds In late Spring And Early Summer.

- Roots or tubers in the soil grow to the surface of the water, creating a wall of vegetation.
- Plants have many branches with each individual branch having a series of leaves growing around the stem in the same plane, like spokes on a bicycle wheel, called whorls.
- Each whorl has 4-8 blade-like leaves with slightly toothed edges around stem.

Hydrilla may look different colors depending on the water condition:

- In brackish water hydrilla will turn brown in early fall; and
- In hard water it may develop a whitish coating of calcium carbonate.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Hydrocharitales

Family: Hydrocharitaceae

Genus : *Hydrilla*

Bangla Name: Kutkute jhanjhi

English Name : Water thyme

Common Name : Hydrilla

Scientific Name : *Hydrila verticillata*

Species: *H. Verticillata*

Water Hyacinths (কচুরিপানা)

Water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*), known locally in some regions as Kochuripana, is a floating aquatic plant native to the Amazon basin. It's characterized by its striking purple flowers, large, waxy leaves, and rapid growth. Here's a detailed description:

➤ Physical Characteristics:

- **Leaves:** Broad, rounded, and glossy, typically about 15-30 cm long. They float on the water's surface, with a bulbous petiole (stem) that helps keep them buoyant.
- **Flowers:** Clusters of beautiful, lavender to purple flowers bloom above the water, each with six petals. They usually have a yellow spot on the lower petal.
- **Roots:** Long, feathery roots hang below the water, providing stability and helping in nutrient absorption.

➤ Growth Habit:

Water hyacinth can grow in dense mats, covering large areas of water bodies. It can double its biomass in just a few weeks under favorable conditions, leading to potential ecological issues.

➤ Habitat:

It thrives in freshwater environments such as lakes, rivers, and ponds, preferring nutrient-rich waters.

➤ **Ecological Impact:**

While water hyacinth can provide habitat for fish and other aquatic organisms, its rapid growth can lead to:

- Blockage of waterways: This can disrupt navigation and irrigation.
- Oxygen depletion: As mats die and decompose, they consume oxygen, harming aquatic life.
- Biodiversity loss: It can outcompete native plants, altering ecosystem.

➤ **Uses:**

Despite its invasive nature, water hyacinth has beneficial uses:

- Bioremediation: It can absorb pollutants and heavy metals from water.
- Crafts and Biomaterials: The plant is used to make baskets, mats, and other decorative items.
- Animal Feed: It can be used as fodder for livestock when processed correctly. And for Agriculture its uses as fertilizer and keep hold soil moisture.

➤ **Management:**

Controlling water hyacinth involves mechanical removal, biological control (**using specific insects**), and chemical methods, though care must be taken to minimize environmental impact.

Overall, water hyacinth is a fascinating plant with both beneficial and detrimental characteristics, making it important to manage it responsibly in ecosystems where it proliferates

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Liliales

Family: Pontederiaceae

Genus: *Echhornia*

Species: *Crassipes L.*

Bangla Name: কচুরিপানা

English Name: Water Hyacinths

Scientific Name: *Echhornia Crassipes L.*

Buffalo spinach (হেলেঞ্চা)

Enhydra fluctuans commonly known as Helencha shak, is a semi-aquatic herbaceous plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. This perennial species thrives in shallow freshwater habitats, including ponds, marshes, and riverbanks, where it often floats on the surface or grows partially submerged. The leaves are broad and ovate, typically ranging from 5 to 15 cm in length,

featuring a glossy, waxy texture that helps minimize water loss. These leaves can float on water, allowing for effective photosynthesis. Helencha shak produces clusters of small, yellow flower heads composed of numerous florets, attracting various pollinators like bees. The plant can reach heights of 30 to 60 cm, often forming dense mats in optimal conditions, which enhances its ecological role.

- **Growth Habit :** *Enhydra fluctuans* exhibits a semi-aquatic growth habit, thriving in shallow freshwater bodies such as ponds, marshes, and along riverbanks. It can be found floating on the water's surface or partially submerged, giving it a unique appearance in its natural habitat.
- **Leaves**

The leaves of *Helanthes* are distinctive, broad, and ovate, often measuring between 5 to 15 cm in length. They are typically glossy with a waxy texture that helps reduce water loss. The leaves can float on the water, providing buoyancy and maximizing exposure to sunlight for photosynthesis. The margins may be slightly serrated, and the leaves grow in an alternate arrangement along the stem.

➤ **Flowers**

Enhydra fluctuans produces small, yellow flower heads, which are usually grouped in clusters. Each flower head consists of numerous tiny florets, making the plant visually appealing, especially when in full bloom. The flowers are primarily pollinated by insects, attracting bees and other pollinators.

➤ **Height**

The plant can reach heights of 30 to 60 cm, depending on environmental conditions such as water depth and nutrient availability. It can form dense mats in favorable conditions, further contributing to its ecological role.

➤ **Habitat and Distribution**

Enhydra fluctuans is predominantly found in tropical and subtropical regions across Asia, Africa, and parts of the Americas. It thrives in freshwater wetlands, including shallow lakes, ponds, and rice paddies, where it plays a crucial role in the local ecosystem.

➤ **Ecological Significance**

Helanthes is vital to its ecosystem for several reasons:

- **Habitat:** It provides habitat and food for various aquatic organisms, including fish and invertebrates.
- **Water Quality:** The plant contributes to nutrient cycling and can help improve water quality by absorbing excess nutrients and pollutants.
- **Biodiversity:** By forming dense mats, it offers shelter and breeding grounds for numerous species, promoting biodiversity in its habitat.

Uses and Cultural Significance

➤ Culinary Uses

Helencha shak is valued as a culinary ingredient in several cultures, particularly in South Asian cuisine. The young leaves and tender shoots are often used in salads, soups, and curries. They are appreciated for their slightly bitter flavor and high nutritional content, being rich in vitamins and minerals.

➤ Medicinal Uses

Traditionally, *Enhydra fluctuans* has been used in folk medicine for various ailments, including digestive issues, skin problems, and inflammatory conditions. While some studies suggest potential health benefits, more research is needed to validate these uses scientifically.

➤ Economic Importance

In addition to its culinary and medicinal uses, the plant may also be harvested for sale in local markets, contributing to the livelihoods of communities in its native regions.

➤ Cultivation and Management

Enhydra fluctuans can be cultivated in home gardens or aquaponics systems due to its adaptability to wet conditions. It can be propagated through seeds or cuttings. However, care should be taken to manage its growth, as it can become invasive in some areas, potentially disrupting local ecosystem

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Streptophyta

Class: Equisetopsida

Common Name: Helencha

Subclass: Magnoliidae

English Name: Buffalo spinach

Order: Asterales

Scientific Name: *Enhydra fluctuans* L.

Family: Asteraceae

Genus: *Enhydra*, **Species:** *fluctuans* L.

Water spinach (কলমি)

Ipomoea aquatica commonly known as water spinach or kolmi shak, is a versatile aquatic plant belonging to the Convolvulaceae family. Native to tropical and subtropical regions of Asia, it thrives in wetlands, ponds, and along riverbanks. Here's a detailed description:

➤ Physical Characteristics

- **Growth Habit:** This perennial plant can grow as a floating aquatic plant or as a semi-aquatic vine. It often forms dense mats on water surfaces.
- **Leaves:** The leaves are broad, heart-shaped, and vary in size, typically measuring between 5 to 20 cm long. They are dark green, smooth, and have a glossy appearance.
- **Stems:** The stems are hollow and can reach lengths of up to 3 meters, making them buoyant and adaptable to water currents. They often root at the nodes when submerged.
- **Flowers:** The flowers are funnel-shaped and can be white to pale purple, typically measuring 4 to 5 cm across. They bloom in clusters, adding aesthetic value to ponds and water bodies.
- **Seeds:** After flowering, the plant produces small, round seeds that can float on water, aiding in its spread.

➤ Habitat

- **Water Conditions:** It prefers shallow water with slow-moving or stagnant conditions. Water spinach is often found in nutrient-rich environments, making it a common species in rice paddies and wetlands.
- **Temperature:** As a tropical plant, it thrives in warm temperatures, ideally between 20°C to 30°C (68°F to 86°F).

➤ Uses

- **Culinary:** Water spinach is a popular vegetable in many Asian cuisines. The young shoots and leaves are tender and can be stir-fried, steamed, or used in soups. It has a slightly sweet flavor and is rich in vitamins A and C, as well as iron and calcium.
- **Medicinal:** In traditional medicine, parts of the plant are used for their anti-inflammatory and diuretic properties.
- **Ecological:** As an aquatic plant, it plays a role in improving water quality by absorbing excess nutrients and providing habitat for aquatic organisms.

➤ Cultivation

- Water spinach can be easily propagated through stem cuttings. It can also spread rapidly through seeds if conditions are favorable.
- It grows best in sunny locations with rich, loamy soil or directly in water. Regular harvesting promotes bushier growth and prevents flowering.

➤ Environmental Impact

While water spinach has many beneficial uses, it can become invasive in some regions, leading to ecological imbalance by outcompeting native flora. Proper management is essential to prevent its overgrowth in non-native areas.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Spermatophyta

Subphylum: Angiospermae

Class: Dicotyledonae

Order: Solanales

Family: Convolvulaceae

Genus: *Ipomoea*

Species: *aquatica*

Common Name: Kolmi (কলমি)

English Name: Water sponach

Scientific Name: *Ipomoea aquatica* L.

Water lenses or Mosquito fern (কুটিপানা)

Azolla pinnata, commonly known as mosquito fern, belongs to the family Salviniaceae and is a small, floating aquatic fern. It is distributed widely in tropical and subtropical regions across Asia, Africa, and the Americas. The plant thrives in shallow freshwater bodies such as ponds, swamps, and rice paddies.

Morphology: *Azolla pinnata* exhibits a unique morphology characterized by its small, frond-like leaves that are typically less than 1 cm in length. The leaves are divided into lobes, forming a feathery appearance. The upper surface is green and often covered with a layer of microscopic hairs, while the underside is typically reddish or brownish. The plant forms dense mats on the water surface, which can significantly impact light penetration and aquatic ecosystems.

Reproductive Biology: Reproduction in *Azolla pinnata* occurs both sexually and asexually. Asexual reproduction is primarily through fragmentation, where fragments of the plant develop into new individuals. Sexual reproduction involves the formation of gametes in specialized structures, leading to the production of spores. The plant's life cycle is influenced by environmental conditions, with optimal growth occurring in warm temperatures and nutrient-rich waters.

Ecological Role: *Azolla pinnata* plays a crucial role in aquatic ecosystems. It serves as a habitat for various microorganisms, invertebrates, and fish. The dense mats it forms can provide shelter and breeding grounds for aquatic life. Additionally, *Azolla pinnata* contributes to nutrient cycling and has the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen, enriching the water body and supporting the growth of other aquatic plants.

Economic Importance: *Azolla pinnata* has significant economic value. It is used as a biofertilizer in rice cultivation, enhancing soil fertility and reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers. The plant is also a potential source of livestock feed and has been explored for its use in bioremediation processes to absorb excess nutrients and pollutants from water bodies.

Challenges and Management: While *Azolla pinnata* offers various benefits, its rapid growth can lead to ecological imbalances, such as oxygen depletion and decreased biodiversity. Effective management strategies, including controlled cultivation and monitoring of its spread, are essential to mitigate potential negative impacts.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Polypodiophyta

Class: Polypodiopsida

Order: Salviniiales

Family: Salviniaceae

Genus: *Azolla*

Species: *A.pinnata*

Common Name: Kutipana

English Name: Water lenses or Mosquito fern

Scientific Name: *Azolla Pinnata*

Rootless duckweed (সুজিপানা)

Wolffia arrhiza is a minute, floating aquatic plant, typically measuring 0.5 to 1 mm in diameter. Its body is globular and lacks true leaves and stems, which contributes to its streamlined appearance. The plant is green due to chlorophyll and may exhibit a slightly hairy texture.

➤ Habitat and Distribution

This species thrives in warm, shallow freshwater environments such as ponds, marshes, and slow-moving streams. It is distributed globally, often found in tropical and subtropical regions, where it can form dense mats on water surfaces.

➤ Reproductive Biology

Wolffia arrhiza reproduces both asexually through vegetative fragmentation and sexually via tiny, inconspicuous flowers. The reproductive structures are borne on the surface of the plant, facilitating pollination and seed dispersal in aquatic ecosystems.

➤ Ecological Role

As a primary producer, *Wolffia arrhiza* plays a critical role in aquatic food webs, supporting various herbivores. Its rapid growth can also contribute to oxygen production and provide habitat for microorganisms.

➤ **Economic Importance**

While not widely cultivated, *Wolffia arrhiza* is studied for its potential in bioengineering and sustainable agriculture due to its high protein content and rapid growth rate. Its use in aquaculture and as a potential food source is also being explored.

➤ **Challenges and Conservation**

Habitat loss due to pollution and water management practices poses a threat to *Wolffia arrhiza* populations. Conservation efforts are necessary to maintain its ecological role and genetic diversity.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Wolffia*

Species: *W. arrhiza*

Common Name: Sujipana (সুজিপানা)

English Name: Rootless duckweed

Scientific Name: *Wolffia arrhiza*

Common duckweed (তেতুলিয়াপানা / খুদিপানা)

Lemna minor, commonly known as common duckweed, is a small, floating aquatic plant belonging to the family Araceae. It features a simple structure, typically comprising a few oval to round green fronds, each measuring 1-4 mm in diameter. The plant lacks a true stem, with fronds arising directly from a single, submerged root system that helps anchor it to the water body. Its roots are delicate and can extend several centimeters into the water, providing stability and facilitating nutrient absorption.

Habitat and Distribution

Lemna minor is widely distributed across temperate regions worldwide, thriving in shallow ponds, lakes, and slow-moving water bodies. It prefers nutrient-rich environments, often colonizing areas with high nitrogen and phosphorus levels. This adaptability allows it to flourish in diverse aquatic habitats, from freshwater lakes to rice paddies.

Ecological Role

As a key player in aquatic ecosystems, *Lemna minor* contributes to water quality by absorbing excess nutrients and reducing algal blooms. Its dense growth can provide habitat and food for various organisms, including fish and invertebrates. However, when overabundant, it can also lead to reduced light penetration and oxygen depletion in water, affecting overall biodiversity.

Reproductive Biology

Lemna minor exhibits both asexual and sexual reproduction. Asexual reproduction occurs through vegetative propagation, where new fronds bud from existing ones, leading to rapid population growth. Under favorable conditions, it can form extensive mats that cover water surfaces. Sexual reproduction is less common but involves the formation of flowers that produce seeds, contributing to genetic diversity within populations.

Applications and Benefits

Lemna minor has gained attention for its potential applications in water treatment, as it can effectively remove pollutants from wastewater. Additionally, its high protein content makes it a promising candidate for animal feed and aquaculture. Research is ongoing to explore its use in biofuel production and as a sustainable food source for humans.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Arales

Family: Lemnaceae

Genus: Lemna

Species: *minor* L.

Common Name: Tetuliapana (তেতুলিয়াপানা)

English Name: Common duckweed

Scientific Name: *Lemna minor* L.

Water lily (শাপলা)

Water lilies belonging to the genus *Nymphaea*, are iconic aquatic plants known for their striking flowers and broad, floating leaves. Found in freshwater habitats across the globe, these plants are particularly prevalent in shallow lakes, ponds, and slow-moving rivers. The diverse range of species within the genus showcases a variety of flower colors, sizes, and forms, making them popular in ornamental gardening and water features.

Morphology and Anatomy

Water lilies exhibit a unique morphological structure that allows them to thrive in aquatic environments. The leaves, often large and round, float on the water's surface, supported by long, flexible petioles that anchor them to the sediment below. These leaves can vary in color from green to purplish hues, often featuring distinctive patterns that add visual interest. The flowers, which can be white, yellow, pink, or blue, typically bloom during the day or night depending on the species. Each flower consists of numerous petals surrounding a central cluster of stamens and carpels, making them a key feature for pollinators.

Ecological Role

Water lilies play a significant role in their ecosystems. Their floating leaves provide shade and shelter for fish and other aquatic organisms, helping to regulate water temperatures and reduce algae growth by limiting sunlight penetration. The plants also contribute to the overall biodiversity of their habitats, offering food and refuge for various species. Additionally, their root systems help stabilize sediments, mitigating erosion in shorelines.

Cultivation and Uses

Cultivating water lilies can enhance garden aesthetics and promote biodiversity. They are often used in ornamental ponds and water gardens, where they can thrive with minimal maintenance. Beyond their ornamental value, water lilies have been utilized in traditional medicine across various cultures, with different parts of the plant used for their purported therapeutic properties.

Conservation Concerns

Despite their resilience, water lilies face threats from habitat loss, pollution, and climate change. Invasive species can outcompete native populations, disrupting local ecosystems. Conservation efforts are essential to preserve these beautiful plants and the ecological benefits they provide.

➤ **Roots**

Structure: Water lilies have a fibrous root system that anchors them to the substrate in shallow waters.

Function: Roots absorb nutrients and help stabilize the plant in sediment, allowing it to withstand water movement.

➤ **Rhizome**

Structure: The rhizome is a horizontal, creeping stem that grows underground. It serves as the main storage organ.

Function: It stores nutrients and energy, enabling the plant to survive adverse conditions and facilitating vegetative reproduction.

➤ **Leaves**

Structure: Water lily leaves are typically large, round, and flat, with a waxy surface that helps repel water. Water lily leaves vary significantly in size depending on the species. Generally, the leaves can range from about 4 inches (**10 cm**) to over 3 feet (**1 meter**) in diameter.

Function: Floating on the surface, they capture sunlight for photosynthesis and provide shade to aquatic habitats. The broad shape helps reduce water currents' impact.

➤ **Stems (Petioles)**

Structure: Long, flexible petioles connect the leaves to the rhizome. They can elongate to raise the leaves above water.

Function: These stems provide buoyancy and allow the leaves to float freely while also supporting the plant structure.

➤ **Flowers**

Structure: Water lily flowers are large, with numerous petals arranged in a spiral pattern. They may be fragrant and come in various colors.

Function: Flowers are crucial for reproduction, attracting pollinators like bees and beetles. Depending on the species, they may open during the day or at night.

➤ Reproductive Structures

Structure: The flower contains stamens (male) and carpels (female) that facilitate pollination and seed development.

Function: After pollination, flowers develop seeds, which can be dispersed to create new plants, ensuring the continuation of the species.

kingdom: Plantae

phylum: Tracheophyta

class: Magnoliopsida

order: Nymphaeales

family: Nymphaeaceae

genus: Nymphaea

Species: *nouchali*

Common Name: Shapla (শাপলা)

English Name: Water lilies

Scientific Name: *Nymphaea nouchali*

Lotus (পদ্ম)

Morphology and Anatomy The lotus flower is renowned for its striking beauty and unique morphology. Characterized by its broad, round leaves and large, fragrant blooms, the lotus can be aquatic or semi-aquatic, thriving in freshwater environments.

Leaves: The leaves are typically large, circular, and floating, often measuring up to 60 cm in diameter. They are waxy and resilient, enabling them to repel water—an adaptation known as the "lotus effect," which minimizes dirt accumulation.

Flowers: Lotus flowers emerge above the water on sturdy stalks, showcasing a range of colors, including white, pink, yellow, and blue. The flowers can reach up to 20 cm in diameter and feature

numerous petals that arrange in a spiraled pattern around a central cluster of stamens and a prominent ovary.

Roots and Rhizomes: The plant's roots and rhizomes are submerged in sediment, providing stability and nutrient uptake. The rhizome is an essential storage organ, allowing the plant to survive adverse conditions.

Ecological Significance Lotus flowers play a crucial role in aquatic ecosystems. They provide habitat and food for various organisms, including fish, insects, and birds. Their extensive root systems help stabilize sediments and improve water quality by absorbing nutrients.

Cultural and Symbolic Importance The lotus has significant cultural and spiritual symbolism across various traditions. In Buddhism, it represents purity and enlightenment, as it rises pristine from murky waters. In Hinduism, the lotus symbolizes divine beauty and fertility, often associated with deities like Lakshmi and Vishnu.

Medicinal and Nutritional Value Various parts of the lotus plant are used in traditional medicine and culinary practices. The seeds and rhizomes are rich in nutrients and have been used for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-diabetic properties. Lotus tea, made from dried flowers, is also popular for its calming effects.

Conservation and Threats Despite its resilience, the lotus faces threats from habitat destruction, pollution, and climate change. Conservation efforts are essential to preserve this iconic plant and its ecological benefits.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliopsida

Class: Tracheophyta

Order: Proteales

Family: Nelumbonaceae

Genus: Nelumbo

Species: *N. Nucifera*

Common Name: Padma (পদ্ম)

English Name: Lotus

Scientific Name: *Nelumbo nucifera*

Common spike-rush (নলখাগরা পানি ঘাস)

Morphology

Growth Habit: *Eleocharis palustris* typically grows as a clump-forming, grass-like plant. It can reach heights of about 30 to 90 cm (1 to 3 feet).

Stems: The stems are cylindrical, solid, and can be erect or somewhat creeping. They are usually smooth and can vary in color from green to brownish.

Leaves: The leaves are slender and linear, often reduced in size compared to the stems. They are typically basal and may be up to 30 cm long. The leaf blades are often 1-2 mm wide.

Flowers: The inflorescence is a spike, composed of dense clusters of small, green to brown flowers that appear at the tips of the stems. The flowering period usually occurs in late summer to early fall.

Fruit: The fruit is a small, elongated achene that is typically brown when mature. Each spike can produce several fruits.

➤ Habitat

Distribution: *Eleocharis palustris* is found in a variety of wetland habitats, including marshes, riverbanks, and ditches. It prefers shallow water and can grow in both freshwater and brackish environments.

Soil Preference: It typically grows in saturated soils, often in areas that are periodically flooded.

➤ Ecological Importance

Habitat: This plant serves as an important habitat for various aquatic and semi-aquatic species, including birds, insects, and amphibians.

Erosion Control: Its root system helps stabilize soil and prevent erosion in wetland areas.

➤ **Uses**

Ornamental: *Eleocharis palustris* can be used in landscaping, particularly in rain gardens or wetland restoration projects.

Cultural: In some cultures, the plant has been used for various traditional purposes, including weaving.

➤ **Cultivation**

Propagation: It can be propagated by seeds or by division of clumps.

Care: Requires consistently moist soil and can benefit from occasional thinning to maintain healthy growth.

Kingdom:	Plantae
Clade:	Tracheophytes
Clade:	Angiosperms
Clade:	Monocots
Order:	Poales
Family:	Cyperaceae
Genus:	<i>Eleocharis</i>
Species:	<i>E. palustris</i>

Common Name: Nolkhagra (পানিঘাস)

English Name: Common spike-rush

Scientific Name: *Eleocharis palustris*

Water chestnuts (পানিফল)

Water chestnut, known as "paniphal" in some regions, is a versatile aquatic plant belonging to the family Cyperaceae. Its scientific name is *Trapa natans*. This plant thrives in shallow water bodies like ponds, lakes, and marshes, primarily in Asia and parts of Europe.

Description

Physical Appearance: Water chestnut is characterized by its distinctive triangular-shaped tubers, which can grow up to 5 centimeters in length. The tubers are often dark brown or black on the outside, with a white or creamy interior. The plant produces long, floating leaves that can reach up to 40 centimeters in length. These leaves have a smooth, waxy surface and are usually green, providing a vibrant contrast to the muddy waters in which they grow. In summer, it also produces small, white or yellow flowers that emerge above the water's surface.

Habitat: Water chestnuts prefer still or slow-moving water with a rich organic content. They are often found in freshwater environments, thriving in temperatures ranging from 20°C to 30°C. The plants can spread rapidly, forming dense mats that can cover large areas of water, which can impact local ecosystems.

Culinary Uses

Water chestnuts are highly valued in various cuisines, particularly in Asian dishes. They are typically harvested for their crunchy, tuberous roots, which can be eaten raw, boiled, or stir-fried. They add a unique texture to dishes and are often found in salads, stir-fries, and dumplings. Their mild, slightly sweet flavor makes them a versatile ingredient in both savory and sweet recipes.

Nutritional Benefits

Nutritionally, water chestnuts are low in calories and rich in fiber, making them a healthy choice for various diets. They contain essential nutrients such as potassium, vitamin B6, and antioxidants. The high water content helps with hydration and digestion.

Cultural Significance

In addition to their culinary uses, water chestnuts hold cultural significance in many regions. In some cultures, they are associated with prosperity and are often used in festive dishes during celebrations.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnoliopsida

Subclass: Rosidae

Order: Myrtales

Family: Trapaceae

Genus: *Trapa*

Species: *Natans*

Common Name: Paniphol (পানিফল)

English Name: Water chestnut

Scientific Name: *Trapa natans*

Freshwater mangrove (হিজল)

Barringtonia acutangula, commonly known as the freshwater mangrove is a tropical tree belonging to the Lecythidaceae family.

General Characteristics

Growth Habit: *Barringtonia acutangula* is a large, evergreen tree that can reach heights of 10 to 20 meters (33 to 66 feet). It typically has a broad, spreading crown.

Bark: The bark is smooth and grayish-brown, often with a slightly flaking texture.

Leaves

Arrangement: The leaves are arranged spirally and are large, measuring between 10 to 30 cm (4 to 12 inches) long.

Shape: They are elliptical to ovate, with a pointed tip and a glossy surface. The leaves have a prominent midrib and lateral veins.

Flowers

Inflorescence: The flowers are borne in large, fluffy panicles, typically appearing in clusters.

Color: Each flower has numerous long, staminal filaments that give them a striking appearance, often white or pale pink, sometimes with hints of purple.

Fragrance: The flowers are known for their pleasant fragrance and attract various pollinators, including bees.

Fruit

Structure: The fruit is a distinctive, elongated capsule, typically measuring 8 to 15 cm (3 to 6 inches) in length.

Seed Dispersal: When mature, the fruit dehisces to release seeds, which are buoyant and can float on water, facilitating their dispersal in aquatic environments.

Habitat

Growing Conditions: *Barringtonia acutangula* is commonly found in freshwater swamps, along riverbanks, and in floodplain forests. It prefers wet, tropical climates.

Ecological Role: This tree plays a vital role in stabilizing riverbanks and providing habitat for various wildlife, including birds and insects.

Uses

Cultural Significance: The seeds are sometimes used in traditional medicine, and the wood is utilized for making furniture and crafts.

Ornamental: Due to its attractive flowers and large leaves, it is also planted as an ornamental tree in parks and gardens.

Conservation

Status: While not currently considered endangered, habitat loss due to deforestation and development can impact its populations.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Tracheophyta

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Ericales

Family: Lecythidaceae

Genus: Barringtonia

Species: acutangula

Common Name: Hizol (হিজল)

English Name: Freshwater mangrove

Scientific Name: *Barringtonia acutangula*

Taro (পানিকচু)

Morphology

Leaves: The leaves can grow up to 3 feet long and 2 feet wide, characterized by their large, glossy, dark green appearance. The leaf petioles are long and sturdy, often exhibiting a reddish tinge.

Corms: The edible part of the plant is the corm, which is a starchy underground tuber. It can vary in size, typically round to oval, with a rough brown exterior and white to purple flesh.

Flowers: Taro produces inflorescences that are somewhat inconspicuous compared to the leaves. The flowers are borne on a spike surrounded by a large spathe, which can be green or purplish.

Habitat

Growth Conditions: *Colocasia esculenta* thrives in warm, humid environments. It prefers wet, marshy areas and can often be found in shallow water or well-drained soils with high organic content.

Distribution: This plant is native to Southeast Asia and parts of the Indian subcontinent but is now cultivated worldwide in tropical and subtropical regions.

Uses

Culinary: Taro corms are a staple food in many cultures, consumed in various forms such as boiled, mashed, or made into flour. Taro leaves are also edible and can be cooked similarly to spinach.

Cultural Significance: In many Pacific Island cultures, taro holds cultural importance and is often featured in traditional dishes and rituals.

Care and Cultivation

Planting: Taro is typically propagated from corms. It requires a growing season with plenty of moisture, making it well-suited for wetlands or irrigated fields.

Pests and Diseases: Taro can be susceptible to pests like taro beetles and diseases such as leaf blight. Proper management and crop rotation can help mitigate these issues.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Clade: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Colocasia*

Species: *esculenta*

Common Name: Pnikochu (পানিকচু)

English Name: Taro

Scientific Name: *Colocasia esculenta*

Grassy pondweed (জলজ আগাছা)

Potamogeton gramineus, commonly known as slender pondweed or grass-leaved pondweed, is a perennial aquatic plant found in freshwater habitats such as lakes, ponds, and slow-moving rivers. Here's a detailed description:

Morphology

Leaves: The leaves are linear and grass-like, typically ranging from 3 to 25 cm in length. They are narrow, elongated, and have a smooth texture, often appearing in whorls or alternately along the stem. The leaf edges are generally entire (smooth) and can have a slight waxy sheen.

Stems: The stems are slender, flexible, and can grow to be several meters long. They may float on the water's surface or be submerged, providing a habitat for various aquatic organisms.

Flowers: *Potamogeton gramineus* produces small, inconspicuous flowers that are typically found on slender spikes. The flowers bloom above the water surface, usually from late spring to early summer. Each spike can contain several small flowers, which are generally greenish or pale yellow.

Fruit: The fruit is a small, oval-shaped achene that is dispersed by water currents.

Habitat

Potamogeton gramineus thrives in a variety of freshwater environments, often in areas with moderate to high nutrient levels. It prefers shallow waters but can grow in depths of up to 2 meters. It often forms dense beds, providing critical habitat for fish and invertebrates.

Ecology

Role in Ecosystem: This species plays a vital role in aquatic ecosystems, offering food and shelter for various wildlife, including fish, birds, and insects. The dense growth can help stabilize sediments and reduce erosion.

Pollination: The flowers are primarily wind-pollinated, although some insect visitation may occur.

Distribution

Potamogeton gramineus is widely distributed across North America, Europe, and parts of Asia. It is often found in both natural and disturbed freshwater systems.

Conservation

While generally not considered endangered, *Potamogeton gramineus* can be affected by habitat loss, pollution, and the introduction of invasive species. Maintaining healthy aquatic ecosystems is crucial for the conservation of this species and its habitat.

Uses

In addition to its ecological significance, *Potamogeton gramineus* may be used in water gardens and aquariums. Its presence can enhance the aesthetic appeal of water features while providing ecological benefits.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Clade: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Potamogetonaceae

Genus: Potamogeton

Common Name: Joloj agacha

English Name: Grassy pondweed

Scientific Name: *Potamogeton gramineus*

Species: *P. gramineus*

Curly pondweed (কোঁকড়া পাতা)

Curly pondweed (*Potamogeton crispus*) is a submerged aquatic plant commonly found in freshwater habitats such as ponds, lakes, and slow-moving rivers. This perennial species is known for its distinctive, curly leaves, which can vary in shape but are typically lanceolate (spear-like) and have a wavy or crinkled appearance. The leaves can grow up to 20 centimeters (about 8 inches) in length and are arranged in a whorled pattern around the stem.

Habitat and Distribution: Curly pondweed thrives in nutrient-rich waters and can tolerate a range of environmental conditions, often found in shallow areas with moderate to high light levels. It is native to parts of Europe and Asia but has been widely introduced to North America and other regions.

Reproduction: This plant reproduces both sexually through flowers and asexually via fragments and tubers. The small, inconspicuous flowers bloom in late spring to early summer, emerging above the water on slender stalks. The plant can also spread rapidly through its vegetative parts, making it a resilient species.

Ecological Role: Curly pondweed plays a significant role in its ecosystem. It provides habitat and food for various aquatic organisms, including fish, invertebrates, and waterfowl. Additionally, it helps stabilize sediment and improve water quality by absorbing excess nutrients.

Management Concerns: While curly pondweed can be beneficial, it can also become invasive in some areas, leading to dense growth that may obstruct navigation, reduce water flow, and outcompete native species. Effective management strategies are essential in regions where it poses a threat to local biodiversity.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Najadales

Family: Potamogetonaceae

Genus: Potamogeton

Species: *P. crispus*

Common Name: Kokrapata (কোঁকড়া পাতা)

English Name: Curly pondweed

Scientific Name: *Potamogeton crispus*

Banana lily (চন্দ্রমালা)

Nymphoides aquatica, commonly known as the floating heart or water snowflake, is a fascinating aquatic plant native to North America. Here's a detailed description of its characteristics and habitat:

Appearance

Leaves: The leaves are heart-shaped, floating on the water's surface. They can grow up to 10 cm (4 inches) wide and are typically bright green, with a smooth texture and a slightly wavy margin.

Flowers: The plant produces small, delicate flowers that are typically white or pale yellow, with fringed petals. Each flower is about 2-3 cm (0.8-1.2 inches) in diameter and rises above the water on slender stalks. They bloom in summer and attract various pollinators.

Roots: *Nymphoides aquatica* has fibrous roots that anchor it in the substrate while allowing its leaves and flowers to float freely on the water's surface.

Habitat

Distribution: This plant is commonly found in shallow, slow-moving waters, such as ponds, lakes, and marshes, primarily in the eastern United States and parts of Canada.

Growing Conditions: It thrives in sunny to partially shaded environments and prefers calm waters rich in nutrients. It can tolerate a range of water conditions, from slightly acidic to alkaline.

Ecological Role

Habitat: *Nymphoides aquatica* provides critical habitat for various aquatic organisms, including fish, amphibians, and invertebrates. Its floating leaves create shade and reduce water temperature, benefiting the local ecosystem.

Water Quality: The plant plays a role in improving water quality by absorbing excess nutrients and providing oxygen through photosynthesis.

Cultivation and Care

Aquatic Gardens: It can be cultivated in garden ponds and aquariums, where it adds aesthetic appeal. It can be grown in containers or directly in the substrate of shallow water bodies.

Maintenance: While it is relatively low-maintenance, care should be taken to control its growth, as it can spread rapidly under favorable conditions.

Uses

Ornamental: *Nymphoides aquatica* is often used in landscaping for water features due to its attractive foliage and flowers.

Traditional Uses: In some cultures, parts of the plant have been used in traditional medicine, though care should be taken to verify safety and efficacy.

Overall, *Nymphoides aquatica* is a beautiful and ecologically important aquatic plant, ideal for enhancing natural and artificial water environments.

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Eudicots

Clade: Asterids

Order: Asterales

Family: Menyanthaceae

Genus: *Nymphoides*

Species: *aquatica*

Common Name: Chandramala (চন্দ্রমালা)

English Name: Banana lily

Scientific Name: *Nymphoides aquatica*

heartleaf false pickerelweed (বড়নখা)

Monochoria hastata, commonly known as heartleaf false pickerelweed, is an intriguing aquatic perennial plant belonging to the family Pontederiaceae. It is primarily found in freshwater wetlands, marshes, and shallow water bodies.

Morphology:

Leaves: The plant features distinctive heart-shaped leaves that can grow up to 20 cm long. The leaves are usually glossy and have a rich green color, providing a striking contrast against the water.

Flowers: Heartleaf false pickerelweed produces delicate, showy inflorescences. The flowers are typically pale blue to lavender and consist of three petals arranged in a star-like formation. They bloom in clusters on slender stalks that rise above the water, usually during the summer months, attracting various pollinators such as bees and butterflies.

Roots and Stems: The plant has a fibrous root system that anchors it securely in the substrate. The stems are usually erect and can reach heights of about 50 cm.

Habitat

Distribution: Heartleaf false pickerelweed is commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions, particularly in parts of Southeast Asia and Africa. It thrives in freshwater environments, often in slow-moving waters or seasonal wetlands.

Ecological Role: This species plays a vital role in its habitat by providing shelter and food for aquatic organisms. Its leaves and flowers contribute to the overall biodiversity of wetland ecosystems and help improve water quality by stabilizing sediments and filtering nutrients.

Cultivation

Growing Conditions: Heartleaf false pickerelweed prefers full sun to partial shade and grows best in nutrient-rich, moist soils. It can tolerate a range of water depths but thrives in shallow water where it can spread and establish.

Uses: In addition to its ecological benefits, the plant is sometimes used in ornamental gardens and water features due to its attractive foliage and flowers. It can also be a beneficial addition to naturalized landscaping.

Conservation

While not currently considered endangered, heartleaf false pickerelweed can be impacted by habitat loss and water pollution. Conservation efforts focus on protecting wetland habitats and promoting sustainable land-use practices to ensure the health of this and other aquatic species.

In summary, *Monochoria hisitata* is a beautiful and ecologically significant aquatic plant that enhances wetland biodiversity and offers aesthetic value in garden design.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Clade: Monocots

Order: Poales

Family: Pontederiaceae

Genus: *Monochoria*

Species: *M hastata*

Common Name: Boronakha

English Name: heartleaf false pickerelweed

Scientific Name: *Monochoria Hastata*

Brittle water nymph (নাজাস)

Appearance

The Brittle Water Nymph typically has a slender, almost fragile frame that reflects its delicate nature. Its skin shimmers with a translucent quality, resembling the surface of a gently rippling stream. Colors vary from pale blues and greens to iridescent whites, mimicking the hues of water. The nymph's hair flows like liquid, often cascading in waves that mimic the movement of water, adorned with tiny aquatic plants, flowers, or shimmering droplets.

Habitat

These water nymphs inhabit serene bodies of water such as lakes, rivers, and ponds, often found in secluded, enchanting locations. Their homes are surrounded by lush vegetation, where the air is thick with the scent of damp earth and blooming flora. They thrive in environments that are clean and well-preserved, reflecting their connection to the purity of water.

Personality

Brittle Water Nymphs are known for their gentle and elusive demeanor. They are often shy, preferring to observe from a distance rather than engage directly with intruders. Despite their delicate appearance, they possess a strong affinity for nature and are fiercely protective of their watery domains. They are also known for their playful spirit, often engaging in lighthearted mischief when the mood strikes.

Powers and Abilities

These nymphs are believed to have control over water, able to influence its flow and clarity. They can summon gentle rains, create mesmerizing ripples on the surface, or even heal aquatic life. Their ethereal songs can enchant creatures, drawing them closer to the water's edge. However, their powers are closely tied to the health of their environment; if the waters are polluted or harmed, the nymphs weaken.

Symbolism

In various cultures, Brittle Water Nymphs symbolize purity, serenity, and the fragility of nature. They remind us of the importance of caring for our ecosystems and the interconnectedness of all living things. Their presence often serves as a warning against overexploitation of natural resources.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Najadales

Family: Najadaceae

Genus: *Najas*

Species: *N minor*

Common Name: *Najas* (নাজাস)

English Name: Brittle waternymph

Scientific Name: *Najas minor* L.

Yellow Lotus (গোমতী)

Nelumbo lutea, commonly known as the American lotus or yellow lotus, is a perennial aquatic plant native to North America. Here are some key characteristics:

Habitat: It typically grows in shallow waters, such as ponds, lakes, and slow-moving rivers, often in muddy or sandy substrates.

Leaves: The leaves are large, circular, and can float on the water's surface. They can reach up to 2 feet (60 cm) in diameter and are distinctive for their ability to rise above the water.

Flowers: The flowers are large and striking, usually bright yellow, and can be up to 10 inches (25 cm) across. They have numerous petals arranged in a cup shape and typically bloom from mid-summer to early fall.

Fruit: The fruit is a distinctive seed pod that resembles a showerhead, containing several seeds that are edible and can be used in various culinary applications.

Cultural significance: The plant holds cultural importance in many Indigenous communities and is often used in traditional dishes and medicine.

Nelumbo lutea is not only beautiful but also plays a crucial role in its ecosystem, providing habitat and food for various wildlife species.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Streptophyta

Class: Equisetopsida

Subclass: Magnoliidae

Order: Proteales

Family: Nelumbonaceae

Genus: *Nelumbo*

Species: *N. lutea*

Common Name: Gomoti

English Name: Yellow Lotus

Scientific Name: *Nelumbo lutea*

Creeping woodsorrel (আমরুল শাক)

Creeping woodsorrel (*Oxalis corniculata*) is a perennial herbaceous plant known for its clover-like leaves and small yellow flowers. Here's a detailed description:

Appearance

Leaves: The plant has trifoliate (three-leaflet) leaves that resemble those of clover. Each leaflet is heart-shaped to oval, bright green, and about 1–2 cm long.

Stems: The stems are thin and creeping, often rooting at the nodes, allowing the plant to spread along the ground.

Flowers: The small, bright yellow flowers typically bloom from late spring to fall. Each flower has five petals, and they are about 1–2 cm across. Sometimes the flowers can be pale or white, depending on the specific variety or growing conditions.

Fruit: The plant produces small, elongated seed pods that can explosively release seeds when mature.

Habitat

Creeping woodsorrel is commonly found in a variety of habitats, including lawns, gardens, and disturbed areas. It thrives in moist, well-drained soil and can tolerate a range of light conditions, from full sun to partial shade.

Uses

While often considered a weed in gardens and lawns, creeping woodsorrel is edible. The leaves and flowers have a tangy flavor due to their oxalic acid content, which can add a zesty note to salads and dishes.

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

Class: Magnoliosida

Order: Oxalidales

Family: Oxalidaceae

Genus: Oxalis

Species: *O corniculata*

Common Name: Amrul shak

English Name: Creeping woodsorrel

Scientific name: *Oxalis corniculata*

Conclusion

Here I have mentioned many aquatic plants. Which I observed from different parts of the village. And I have briefly described all the information collected from various journals and sites. So that everyone can benefit from this information in brief.

Aquatic plants are fundamental to the health and functionality of both freshwater and marine ecosystems. They serve multiple ecological roles, including providing habitat and food for various aquatic organisms, such as fish, invertebrates, and amphibians. Their extensive root systems stabilize sediments, preventing erosion and promoting clear water conditions, which are essential for the survival of many aquatic species.

Furthermore, aquatic plants play a critical role in nutrient cycling by absorbing excess nutrients, thereby helping to mitigate problems such as eutrophication. Through photosynthesis, they produce oxygen, which is vital for the survival of aquatic life. The presence of diverse aquatic vegetation also enhances water quality, reduces pollutants, and provides shade that helps regulate temperature, creating a more hospitable environment for fish and other organisms.

Reference

1. (Hydrilla fragments) (<https://dec.ny.gov/nature/animals-fish-plants/hydrilla>, n.d.) (htt2)
(Chris Evans & Joseph LaForest, 2014),
2. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Main_Page, 2024)
3. (Royal Botanic Garden Kew), (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>),
(Prasanta Bhowmik^{1*}, 2023), (Prasanta Bhowmik^{1*}, Enhydra fluctuans
Lour: A Comprehensive Review on Its Ethnobotanical and
Pharmacological Uses, 2023)
4. (Dueñas-López, Ipomoea aquatica (swamp morning-glory), 2023)
5. (Gettys, <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>, 2024)
6. (<https://www.invasive.org/index.cfm>)
7. (Royal Botanic Garden Kew) (Keim, 2011)
8. (Animal and Plant Health Inspection Services)
9. (<https://www.wildlifetrusts.org/>, n.d.)
10. (Mahmud, Identity of Water Chestnut (Paniphal) In Bangladesh, 2024)
11. (Barringtonia acutangula), (Animal and Plant Health Inspection
Services, n.d.)
12. (<https://www.invasive.org/index.cfm>, n.d.)
13. (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>, n.d.)